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Covid-19 vaccination and IgG antibody kinetics

Case report

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Abstract

Background:

A novel severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) pandemic is still doing great damage.

Methods:

In follow up, the behaviour of Covid-19 vaccine induced IgG antibodies of a 30-40 year young and healthy women have been investigated.

Results:

The natural decline of Covid-19 vaccine induced IgG antibodies of a healthy young woman is very impressive.

Conclusion:

Today's Covid-19 vaccination strategy should be re-considered.

Keywords: Covid-19; Vaccination; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship; Causality; Causation

1. Introduction

Coronavirus disease 2019 (Covid-19), which causes various, very serious damage to human health, culture and economy, was first reported in Wuhan (China), the capital of Hubei in the year 2019.¹ Meanwhile, the global coronavirus disease 2019 pandemic has still not come to an end. As of 5:37pm CEST, 3 June 2022, there have been 6.294.969 deaths of COVID-19, including 528.816.317 confirmed cases, reported to WHO. As of 1 June 2022, a total of 11.947.644.522 vaccine doses have been administered.² Vaccination against Covid-19 is one of the many ways to counter this very dangerous disease. However, how effective are these Covid-19 vaccinations (see [Barukčić, 1989, 2016, 2020, 2021a,b, 2022](#)), and how often should the same be repeated?

¹Ahn DG, Shin HJ, Kim MH, Lee S, Kim HS, Myoung J, Kim BT, Kim SJ. Current Status of Epidemiology, Diagnosis, Therapeutics, and Vaccines for Novel Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). *J Microbiol Biotechnol.* 2020 Mar 28;30(3):313-324. doi: 10.4014/jmb.2003.03011. PMID: 32238757.

²WHO Coronavirus (COVID-19) Dashboard

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

2.2. Methods

Definitions should help us to provide and assure a systematic approach to a scientific issue. It also goes without the need of further saying that a definition as such need to be logically consistent and correct.

2.2.1. Kinetics of antibodies

Human immunoglobulin G (IgG) is very heterogeneous and determined by four distinct species of molecules designated IgG 1, IgG 2, IgG 3 and IgG 4. All four of these IgG subclasses are present in normal human serum and are subject to very subtly kinetics. The detailed kinetics of antibody production and of the regulation of the immune response can be found in secondary literature.^{3, 4} In point of fact, antibodies of all classes and subclasses except IgD possess the capacity as originally described by the first Nobel laureate in physiology Emil von Behring to feedback regulate the production of themselves.⁵ Moreover, the IgG antibody-mediated suppression of IgM synthesis is of further importance, IgG antibodies are able to suppress IgM responses (negative feedback regulation).⁶

“In der ersten Phase werden vorwiegend Antikörper vom IgM-Typ produziert. Später treten IgG-produzierende Zellen auf. In dem Maße, wie die IgG-Antikörperproduktion zunimmt, wird die IgM-Antikörperproduktion reduziert, d. h. es besteht ein negativer Feedback-Mechanismus zwischen der IgM- und der IgG-Antikörperproduktion. ”

(see [Warnatz, 1982](#), p. 543)

Translated into broken English: ‘In the first phase, mainly antibodies of the IgM type are produced. Later, IgG-producing cells appear. As IgG antibody production increases, IgM antibody production is reduced, i. e. there is a negative feedback mechanism between IgM and IgG antibody production.’

³Uhr JW, Finkelstein MS. The kinetics of antibody formation. *Prog Allergy*. 1967;10:37-83. PMID: 5333338.

⁴Nossal GJ. Kinetics of antibody formation and regulatory aspects of immunity. *Acta Endocrinol Suppl (Copenh)*. 1975;194:96-116. doi: 10.1530/acta.0.080s096. PMID: 1092122.

⁵Heyman B. Feedback regulation by IgG antibodies. *Immunol Lett*. 2003 Aug 5;88(2):157-61. doi: 10.1016/s0165-2478(03)00078-6. PMID: 12880686.

⁶Bergström JJ, Heyman B. IgG Suppresses Antibody Responses in Mice Lacking CIq, C3, Complement Receptors 1 and 2, or IgG Fc-Receptors. *PLoS One*. 2015 Nov 30;10(11):e0143841. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0143841. PMID: 26619292; PMCID: PMC4664261.

2.2.2. Half-life of antibodies

The notion **half-life** is defined as the amount of time it takes a given quantity to decrease to half of its initial value. The term half-life is commonly used in relation to radioactive decay. However, the same notion can be used to describe other processes of decay too, whether exponential or not. In this context, the kinetic and metabolic properties of human immunoglobulins were investigated by several authors⁷ i.e. by turnover studies using IgG isolated from normal human serum. The average biologic half-life of IgG 1, IgG 2, and IgG 4 has been found to be 21 days, while that of IgG 3 was only 7.1 days.^{8, 9}

2.2.3. Carbon-14 dating

A well-known application of the half-life method is radiocarbon-14 dating. Cosmic rays generate neutrons in the upper atmosphere, which interact with nitrogen-14 in the air to produce carbon-14.¹⁰ Based on this effect, Willard Frank Libby (1908 - 1980) developed the half-life radiocarbon-14 dating method.^{11, 12} As outlined before, carbon-14 is constantly being produced in earth's atmosphere and is incorporated into plants i.e. through photosynthesis. Animals consume plants. Once a plant or an animal dies, the same cease to ingest fresh carbon-14 and carbon-14 undergoes radioactive decay while the half-life of carbon-14 is approximately 5,730±40 years.¹³ As a consequence, measuring the amount of carbon-14 in a specimen conveys information about when an animal or a plant died. Several equivalent formulas describing exponential decay might be found in secondary literature.

⁷Morell A, Terry WD, Waldmann TA. Metabolic properties of IgG subclasses in man. *J Clin Invest.* 1970 Apr;49(4):673-80. doi: 10.1172/JCI106279. PMID: 5443170; PMCID: PMC322522.

⁸Morell A, Terry WD, Waldmann TA. Metabolic properties of IgG subclasses in man. *J Clin Invest.* 1970 Apr;49(4):673-80. doi: 10.1172/JCI106279. PMID: 5443170; PMCID: PMC322522.

⁹SOLOMON A, WALDMANN TA, FAHEY JL. Clinical and experimental metabolism of normal 6.6s gamma-globulin in normal subjects and in patients with macroglobulinemia and multiple myeloma. *J Lab Clin Med.* 1963 Jul;62:1-17. PMID: 13978063.

¹⁰S.A. Korff, On the contribution to the ionization at sea-level produced by the neutrons in the cosmic radiation, *Journal of the Franklin Institute*, Volume 230, Issue 6, 1940, Pages 777-779, ISSN 0016-0032, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-0032\(40\)90838-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-0032(40)90838-9).

¹¹W.F. Libby (1946). Atmospheric Helium Three and Radiocarbon from Cosmic Radiation. *Physical Review.* 69 (11–12): 671–672. doi:10.1103/PhysRev.69.671.2

¹²Anderson EC, Libby WF, Weinhouse S, Reid AF, Kirshenbaum AD, Grosse AV. Radiocarbon From Cosmic Radiation. *Science.* 1947 May 30;105(2735):576-7. doi: 10.1126/science.105.2735.576. PMID: 17746224.

¹³GODWIN, H. Half-life of Radiocarbon. *Nature* 195, 984 (1962). <https://doi.org/10.1038/195984a0>

3. Results

Several types of COVID-19 vaccines (Pfizer-BioNTech [Comirnaty], Moderna, CureVac, Janssen-Johnson & Johnson, Astra-Zeneca, Sputnik-V, and CanSino) and other ¹⁴ have been developed and are more or less effective. A 30-40 year-old, healthy woman has been vaccinated by 3 doses of a Covid-19 vaccine: AstraZeneca and Pfizer-BioNTech [Comirnaty]. Finally, the third dose has been a Pfizer-BioNTech [Comirnaty] vaccine and was given on December, 3 2021. SARS-CVODID-19 S protein IgG antibodies were checked in serum on January 10, 2022 and 141 days later on May 31, 2022. SARS-CVODID-19 S protein IgG antibodies were found to be > 25720 (BAU/ml) on January 10, 2022 and 3475,3 (BAU/ml) on May 31, 2022. Figure 3 is illustrating the kinetic of SARS-CVODID-19 S protein IgG antibodies in the serum of this youn woman. The average biologic half-life of IgG has been set to 21 days. ¹⁵ , ¹⁶

$$N_t = N_0 \times \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{t/t_{1/2}}$$

where

$t_{1/2}$ is the half-life of IgG (about 21 days)

N_t is the remaining quantity after time, t

N_0 is the initial quantity

Through 141 days of follow-up, the decline in severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) IgG antibodies ¹⁷ induced by vaccination has been investigated. A healthy, young woman with a normal immune system is presented with a dramatic drop in IgG antibodies in a very short time. However, even if the binding and neutralizing SARS-CoV-2 antibodies elicited by vaccination persist for more than 6 months, their concentration decreases over time and much more than this. Dimeglio et al. ¹⁸ measured the antibody titers in 8758 healthcare workers (HCWs), vaccinated and unvaccinated, in France (10 June–10 July, 2020) with a quantitative enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) (Wantai Biological Pharmacy Enterprise Co., Ltd, China). Dimeglio et al. found that

¹⁴Drugs and Lactation Database (LactMed) [Internet]. Bethesda (MD): National Library of Medicine (US); 2006–. COVID-19 vaccines. 2022 May 15. PMID: 33355732.

¹⁵Morell A, Terry WD, Waldmann TA. Metabolic properties of IgG subclasses in man. *J Clin Invest.* 1970 Apr;49(4):673-80. doi: 10.1172/JCI106279. PMID: 5443170; PMCID: PMC322522.

¹⁶SOLOMON A, WALDMANN TA, FAHEY JL. Clinical and experimental metabolism of normal 6.6s gamma-globulin in normal subjects and in patients with macroglobulinemia and multiple myeloma. *J Lab Clin Med.* 1963 Jul;62:1-17. PMID: 13978063.

¹⁷Eberhardt KA, Dewald F, Heger E, Giesemann L, Vanshylla K, Wirtz M, Kleipass F, Johannis W, Schommers P, Gruell H, Brensing KA, Müller RU, Augustin M, Lehmann C, Koch M, Klein F, Di Cristanziano V. Evaluation of a New Spike (S)-Protein-Based Commercial Immunoassay for the Detection of Anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG. *Microorganisms.* 2021 Mar 31;9(4):733. doi: 10.3390/microorganisms9040733. PMID: 33807490; PMCID: PMC8067155.

¹⁸Dimeglio C, Herin F, Martin-Blondel G, Miedougé M, Izopet J. Antibody titers and protection against a SARS-CoV-2 infection. *J Infect.* 2022 Feb;84(2):248-288. doi: 10.1016/j.jinf.2021.09.013. Epub 2021 Sep 21. PMID: 34560135; PMCID: PMC8452591.

only a concentration of Covid-19 titres of 1700 binding antibody units per ml (BAU/ml) and above provided full protection against Covid-19.

4. Discussion

Vaccination contributes to the decline in mortality and morbidity of various vaccine-preventable (infectious) diseases (VPD) and is still one of the greatest achievements¹⁹ of public health. Particularly worth mentioning is the direct protection for vaccinated individuals. However, high vaccination coverage rates might lead to herd immunity²⁰ and an indirect protection for the overall community and other valuable effects too. However, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) vaccine induced Covid-19 IgG are subject to a certain natural kinetic. Even if this effect as illustrated by figure 3 is scientifically not really that much surprising, the same effect should have an influence on the frequency of Covid-19 re-vaccinations. Otherwise, an unjustified lack of confidence in vaccines might induce a threat to the success of vaccination programs. Nonetheless, under conditions, where the titres of the protective Covid-19 IgG antibodies either do not rise quickly enough or drop too quickly and to too low, an adequate protection against Covid-19 is presumably no longer given. It seems to be that a Covid-19 vaccination more and earlier is much better than a Covid-19 vaccination later or none Covid-19 vaccination at all. The question also arises whether the amount of vaccine administered per vaccination is sufficient?

5. Conclusion

As long as we, the people, have to wait for vaccines which hopefully might ensure vaccination induced protection for years or even for life, a vaccination strategy should consider among other the mathematical formula: *dosage per vaccination* × *frequency of vaccination* = '*constant*'.

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6. Patient consent for publication

Patient consent for publication has been given.

¹⁹Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Ten great public health achievements—United States, 1900-1999. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep.* 1999 Apr 2;48(12):241-3. PMID: 10220250.

²⁰Fine P, Eames K, Heymann DL. "Herd immunity": a rough guide. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2011 Apr 1;52(7):911-6. doi: 10.1093/cid/cir007. PMID: 21427399.

Conflict of interest statement

No conflict of interest to declare.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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ⁱ<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22Baruk%C4%8Di%C4%87,%20Conference%22>

^j<https://twitter.com/ilijabarukcic?lang=de>

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^lhttps://vixra.org/author/ilija_barukcic

^m<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwf3w1IngcukI00jpw8HTwg>

ⁿ<https://portal.dnb.de/opac/showNextResultSite?currentResultId=%22Barukcic%22%26any¤tPosition=30>